

Radix Entomolaris – A Case Report

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Abstract- Mandibular molars usually have two roots , mesial and Distal. In Rare cases they can have additional root located lingually (the radix entomolaris) or buccally (the radix paramolaris).An awareness and understanding of this unusual root and its root canal morphology can contribute to the success of root canal treatment. This paper describes case report of mandibular first molar with three roots (one mesial and two distal) and four canals (two in mesial and two in distal root).

Keywords: Endodontic treatment, Mandibular molars, Radix entomolaris, Radix paramolaris.

Introduction-

The successful outcome of root canal treatment can be attributed to the presence of unusual root canal morphology. Typically, the permanent mandibular first molar has two roots, the mesial and the distal. Knowledge of the existence of an additional root and its root canal anatomy is crucial for a successful treatment outcome. The prevention or healing of endodontic pathology depends on a thorough chemo-mechanical cleaning and shaping of the root canals before a dense root canal filling with a hermetic seal¹

The presence of an additional third root in permanent mandibular first molars may affect the prognosis of the tooth if it is misdiagnosed. ²

The radix entomolaris (RE) is an extra third root in a mandibular first molar that was initially identified by Carabelli in his literature. Some ethnic groupings are linked to the existence of a distinct RE in the first mandibular molar.

Mandibular first molar which has three roots has a frequency of less than 5% in Indian populations.³

It happens five to more than thirty percent of the time in people who have mongoloid qualities, like Chinese, Eskimos, and Native Americans.

RE has an occurrence of less than 5 % in Indian population so such cases are not routinely found in practice.^(4,5)

Case Report-

An 18-year-old male was referred to Department of conservative Dentistry and Endodontics with the chief complaint of pain in lower right back region of jaw since 1 month. On clinical examination, the tooth (46) was deeply carious and was tender to vertical percussion. (fig- a)The radiograph of the mandibular right first molar showed radiolucency approaching pulp and periapical area of mesial root along with a presence of two distal roots. CBCT was done for confirmation. (fig-b) CBCT revealed presence of three roots. Diagnosis of Symptomatic irreversible pulpitis with symptomatic apical periodontitis with 46 was made and root canal treatment was planned.

a.

B

On first appointment Inferior alveolar nerve block with 2% lignocaine with adrenaline was administered to anaesthetize the mandibular right first molar. Access cavity preparation was done under rubber dam application with an endo-access bur and canal orifices were located with DG 16 endodontic explorer. The fourth distolingual canal orifice was present far from distal root canal orifices. Initial negotiation of the root canals was confirmed with K-file 10. The canal lengths were determined by electronic apex locator and confirmed radiographically with K file 15 size.(fig- c) Canals were cleaned with 2.5% sodium hypochlorite along with 17 % EDTA and shaped with Neo Endo rotary files upto 0.06/25. Calcium hydroxide was used as an intracanal medicament for two weeks and cavity was sealed with temporary restorative material. On second appointment, obturation was done with gutta percha using single cone obturation technique and post endodontic restoration was done with composite.(fig-e)

Fig- a.pre-operative Radiograph, b. CBCT images revealing three roots c. working length radiograph, d.Master cone radiograph, e.Post obturation radiograph.

Discussion –

The exact etiology behind the formation of extra root is not clear. In dysmorphic, supernumerary roots, its formation could be related to external factors during odontogenesis, or to the penetrance of an atavistic gene.

Racial genetic factors impact the deeper expression of a certain gene in eumorphic roots, which leads to a more prominent phenotypic manifestation. Curzon proposed that the "three rooted molar" characteristic had a high degree of genetic penetrance because the trait's occurrence was similar in pure Eskimo and Eskimo/Caucasian mixtures, indicating the trait's dominance.^{6,7} Some ethnic groupings are linked to the existence of a distinct RE in the first mandibular tooth.

In African populations, a maximum frequency of 3% is found, while in Eurasian and Indian populations, the frequency is <5%.

Reports have indicated that the RE occurs frequently in populations that exhibit Mongoloid features, such as American Indians, Chinese, and Eskimo.

With its coronal third fully or partially anchored to the distal root, the RE is positioned distolingually. A "mature" root with a regular length and root canal can differ in size from a short conical extension.

. In most cases, the pulpal extension is radiographically visible. In general, the RE is smaller than the distobuccal and mesial roots and can be separate from, or partially fused with, the other roots.⁸ The detection of an extra root may be aided by clinical examination of the tooth crown and examination of the cervical morphology of the roots using periodontal probing. employing sodium hypochlorite in the pulp chamber and a variety of tools, including the endodontic explorer, pathfinder, DG 16 probe, and micro-opener champagne effect—bubbles created by residual pulp tissue in the canal. an additional cusp (tuberculum paramolare) or a cervical prominence or convexity combined with a more pronounced occlusal distal or distolingual lobe.

A more trapezoidal or rectangular outline form is obtained by extending the triangular aperture cavity to the (disto) lingual. In this regard, visual devices like a loupe, intraoral camera, or dental microscope can be helpful.

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The exact location of the RE canal orifice can be found by looking for a dark line on the pulp chamber floor. Particularly in the apical section of the root (as in a Type III RE), a strong root inclination or canal curvature can result in shape aberrations like

straightening of the root canal or a ledge, which can lead to root canal transportation and loss of working length. Following the RE's relocation and enlargement, the radiography root canal length and curvature were used to guide the first root canal investigation using tiny files (size 10 or less) determination, and the creation of a glide path before preparation, is step-by-step actions that should be taken to avoid procedural errors.

Conclusion-

This variation in the anatomy of permanent mandibular first molars should be recognized by oral health care professionals. The diagnosis made at the outset is critical to the success of the endodontic procedure and prevents treatment failures. Several roots and their morphology can be identified by correctly interpreting radiographs taken at different horizontal angulations. Once the diagnosis is made, the conventional triangular cavity should be modified to a trapezoidal form distolingually in order to locate the orifice of the additional root.

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